

Review

Information Security Awareness of Employees in Ethiopian Banking Sector

Mezgeb Manaye Gebru^{1*}

¹College of Computational Science and Engineering, Department of Computer Science, Unity University, Ethiopia

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract *As threats have matured and information has increased in value, attackers have increased their capabilities and expanded to broader intentions, developed more attack methods and methodologies, and are acting on more diverse motives. The issue is too serious when it comes to financial institutions due to their sensitivity to information security attacks. The general aim of this research was to explore the levels of information security awareness of employees in the banking sector in Ethiopia. A quantitative and qualitative research approach was used. Findings showed that the information security awareness level of Ethiopian private banking sector employees is unsatisfactory and needs improvement through continuous on-the-job training. In addition, the training provided on information security awareness for the employees of the private bank in Ethiopia needs improvement.*

Keywords: Information Security Awareness (ISA), Information Security (IS)

Introduction

Information security (IS) depends on human involvement and this human involvement in information security is directly related to human awareness about information security (Vishal &

Teltumde, 2011). This means that humans involved in a security process need to possess the required knowledge about their security-related roles, and thus need some form of education (Vishal & Teltumde, 2011).

The Banking industry is among the leading industries in Ethiopia, and it is becoming heavily dependent on information communication technologies for its service provision and other purposes (Girum, 2016). Banking business competition has stirred the advancement of services enabled by information technology which in turn increased the information security risk (Abiy& Lemma, 2012). Information security in finance and banking can be increased by striving on certain objectives like availability, integrity, confidentiality, accountability, and assurance (Vishal & Teltumde, 2011).

Many of the threats to an organization's computer systems can be attributed to the behaviour of computer users. Hence, information security threats cannot be prevented, avoided, detected, or eliminated by solely focusing on technological solutions (Furnell, Jusoh & Katsabas, 2006).

The information security issue is the most important one in using the Internet and it becomes more crucial while implementing the Internet in banking sectors ((Vishal & Teltumde, 2011). The risks and threats that compromise the security of the bank system are increasing day by day; due to this, banking and financial services need a high level of information security (Vishal &Teltumde, 2011). Information security is the process by which an organization protects and secures its systems, media and facilities that process and maintains information vital to its operations ((Vishal &Teltumde, 2011).

Information security awareness (ISA) is required in organizations where employees process information in line with its confidentiality, integrity, and availability requirements (Veiga, 2015). Employees must be aware of and understand the information security policy requirements they have to follow to process information securely (Gundu & Flowerday, 2013). Many successful computer crimes could have been prevented if employees were aware of information security (Negussie, 2015). Due to this, information security awareness programs must be established in line with banks' information security policies and relevant measures (Abdyli, 2014).

Problem statement

The banking industry in Ethiopia is being transformed due to the global forces for change including technological innovation, the deregulation of financial services at the national level and international competition. The banking business competition has motivated the advancement of services enabled by information technology which in turn increased the information security risk. These threats to information and information systems can include purposeful attacks, environmental disruptions, and human/machine errors which can result in great harm to the national and economic security interests of the country (Patrick, 2011).

Resulting in this technology transformation and national information security policy in today's Ethiopian banking business, Information security becomes one of the key points for customer attraction, retention, and profitability. Thus, to get national and international competitive advantages, information like other assets must be properly managed. Information is a crucial asset of organizations, and the protection of these assets has become one of the major aspects that organizations have to face. Banks are one of such organizations, where data protection and corporate security are a serious concern (Tse, et al., 2013).

Most information security managers pay more attention to technical issues and solutions such as firewalls, routers, and intrusion detection software while paying less focus on soft issues such as the hazards caused by end-users' lack of information security awareness (Katz, 2005). Da Veiga (2015) argues that information security awareness is required in organizations where employees process information in line with its confidentiality, integrity and availability requirements. Because of this, employees must be aware of and understand the information security policy requirements they have to follow to process information securely (Gundu & Flowerday, 2013).

Employee information security awareness plays an important role in establishing security in the systems. It can be said that it is one of the most important criteria for evaluating the safety of the system (Shulaili 2010). Employees' low level of awareness and lack of knowledge towards information security may put an organization at risk. In addition, the lack of employees' information security awareness is one of the main challenges in designing and implementing an information security management system (Kelemie, 2013).

Local surveys such as that conducted by Abiy and Lemma (2012) showed that information security awareness in the Ethiopian banking sector is unsatisfactory. Consequently, the level of proper information security governance in the banking sector in Ethiopia is a critical area that needs improvement. Therefore, it is important to conduct further research into employees' information security awareness (ISA) in the banking sector to better understand what factors and approaches are applied to create awareness among employees of the banking sector about information security and the techniques and frequency that the banking sector in Ethiopia uses to train its employees about information security. This research, therefore, aims to examine the banking sector employees' awareness of information security (IS) and their perceptions towards information security practices in different private banks in Ethiopia.

Literature review

As defined by Information Security Forum (2007), Security Awareness (SA) is the extent to which staff understand the importance of information security, the level of security required by the organization and their individual security responsibilities, and act accordingly. Siponen (2000) defines the term information security awareness (ISA) as a state where users in an organization are ideally committed to their end-user security guidelines. It is very important as information security techniques or procedures can be misused, misinterpreted, or not used by end-users, thereby losing their real usefulness (Siponen, 2000).

Information security (IS) refers to the protection of the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of computerized data and of the systems that process, maintain and report these data; during processing, storage, and dissemination of output (Krugera & Kearney, 2006). Information security includes organizational aspects, legal aspects, institutionalization, and applications of best practices in addition to security technologies (Bilal et al, 2011). The protection of information assets usually relies on the success of information security plans and the implementation of various security controls as part of such a plan (Krugera & Kearney, 2006).

As stated by Whitman and Mattord (2005), staff errors are rated among the top threats to information assets in organizations. It is essential to convince the information security staff of the imperative need to enforce information security measures (Pfleeger & Pfleeger, 2003). It is essential to ensure that all users are aware of information security threats and concerns, and are

equipped to support organizational security policy in the course of their normal work (British Standards Institute, 1999).

Charlie et al (2007) note an organization that lacks information security awareness cannot detect many obvious security risks. They further stress that this lack of awareness can render sophisticated Internet security technologies useless and expose the organization to enormous risks. Due to the intensified need for improved information security, many organizations have established information security awareness programs/ training to ensure that their employees are informed and aware of security risks, thereby protecting themselves and their profitability (Krugera & Kearney, 2006). As stated Bilal et al (2011), effective user security awareness campaigns can greatly enhance the information security assurance posture of an organization. In light of the above discussion, this paper attempted to address the following research questions:

- What is the level of employees' information security awareness in the Ethiopian banking sector?
- What is the frequency of information security awareness training for employees in Ethiopia bank sector?
- What is the perception of the employees in the banking sector towards information security practices in their respective banks?

Methodology

The general aim of this research was to explore the levels of information security awareness of employees in the banking sector in Ethiopia. The study was conducted using questionnaires and interviews as a method of data collection and mixed research method as a research paradigm. Mixed methods research refers to the research or lines of inquiry that integrates one or more qualitative and quantitative techniques for data collection and analysis. The quantitative approach involves the generation of data in a quantitative form which can be subjected to rigorous quantitative analysis formally and rigidly (Kothari, 2004). It is used to answer questions on relationships within measurable variables to explain, predict, and control a phenomenon (Leedy, 1993). Qualitative collection methods, including interviews, focus groups, participant observation, and open-ended survey items have great potential for exploring new topics, assisting

theory building, and providing context for quantitative data Open-ended questions are used in organizational research to explore, explain, or reconfirm existing ideas (Matthias et al. ,2012).

As part of the quantitative approach, the study used a quantitative questionnaire. The questionnaire contained a total of 50 different questions. It had three sections; the first section was used to perform a vocabulary knowledge test. The selection of concepts in this section was based on the Information Security Breaches Survey conducted by Price Waterhouse Coopers (2009). The second section was used to evaluate banks' information security policy and information security awareness training and the third section was used to evaluate employees' information security awareness. As part of the qualitative approach, the study used a qualitative interview. The interview guide had a total of 12 different open-ended questions in three sections discussed above. The data was collected from employees' of private banks in Ethiopia that were not expert in any information technology-related fields.

A combination of random and non-random sampling methods was used to select the subjects of this study. One type of non-random sampling method is Quota sampling. The researcher employs the ease of access to his sample population by using quota samples; his tallying is at his convenience guide by some evidence of characteristics based on the population of interest (Iker & Kabiru, 2017). Quota sampling was used to select an equal number of branches from 16 different private banks in Ethiopia. Five branches were randomly selected from each private bank. A total of 80 branches of a different private bank was selected for the research. The selection of the respondents in the selected banks was done randomly. A total of 160 respondents was randomly selected, two from each selected branch for the quantitative part and 16 participants were randomly selected for the qualitative part of the research, one from each private bank.

The data obtained through the above tools were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The quantitative analysis was done with the help of appropriate software: SPSS Statistics version 25 and R statistical tools version 4.0.0. Other descriptive statistical analysis tools such as percentages, means, grand means, standard deviation and coefficient of correlation were also used.

Findings

The following section presents the findings of the study under four themes: reaction to vocabulary test, reaction to bank IS policy document, reaction to employee training on ISA and reaction to ISA training frequency.

Figure1: Reaction to Vocabulary test.

The first finding was pertinent to the banking sector employees' vocabulary test as an aid to assess their information security awareness levels and to assist with the identification of suitable areas or topics to be included in an information security awareness training program. As Figure 1 above shows, only 45% of the respondents have a reasonable knowledge of threats linked to information security and security attacks such as phishing, spam, spyware, password spraying, keylogger, social engineering, shoulder surfing, Man-in-the-Middle Attack, Identity theft, Malware, and cybercrime. It was quite surprising that 25% indicated that they do not know what the terms mean, while 30% did not understand the terms altogether.

Figure 2: Reaction to bank IS policy document

The second finding was on the information security policy and information security awareness training of the banks. The Information Security Policy provides an integrated set of protection measures that must be uniformly applied across the finance bank to ensure a secure operating environment for its business operations. Customer Information, organizational information, supporting IT systems, processes, and people that are generating, storing, and retrieving information are important assets of the banks. The availability, integrity, and confidentiality of information are essential in building and maintaining our competitive edge, cash flow, profitability, legal compliance, and respected company image. As figure 2 shows, almost all employees of the banks have security policy documents at hand to ensure the security of their banks, but the implementation rate is unsatisfactory.

Figure 3: Reaction to Employee training on ISA

Information Security awareness training is a formal process for educating employees about a variety of threats to information security. As shown in figure 3 above, an information security awareness training provided for employees in Ethiopia private banking sector was unsatisfactory, because 60% of employees in the banking sector had training on Information Security Awareness.

As shown in Figure 4 below, it is evident that more than 70% of the employees reported that their respective banks provided Information Security Awareness (ISA) training annually and the rest indicated that they did so only once during recruiting their employees. The results obtained suggested that the training provided on information security awareness for the employees of the private banking sector in Ethiopia needs improvement.

Figure 4: Reaction to ISA training frequency

The other finding pertains to the banking sector employees’ perception towards information security awareness. The result that is obtained from this section is summarized as follows:

- Respondents have good knowledge about a strong password but their password management was relatively poor. This is because their password setting, changing time, and protection practices are unsatisfactory. What is surprising is that around 11% of the employees shared their passwords for colleagues.
- Most employees are unable to distinguish whether a website is safe to surf and they have limited knowledge of safe Internet usage.
- The employees' knowledge of information security responsibility, the package of security, and security threats need improvement.
- Most employees had adequate knowledge about emergency procedures if they had difficulty while operating on the system, and they had moderate knowledge about the handling of incidents, but needs improvement.
- The employees did not use encryptions while transferring corporate data.

Conclusion

Information security (IS) is the prime area of concern when using the Internet and is of utmost importance in the banking sector. Recent incidents involving information loss have forced many organizations to consider how they can significantly improve their information security. Employees' information security awareness is one way of overcoming this critical issue. This research aimed to explore the levels of information security awareness of employees in the banking sector in Ethiopia. The results demonstrated that the level of information security awareness (ISA) of bank employees in Ethiopia is unsatisfactory.

Financial organizations like banks are becoming more aware of the potential costs of losing information/data. However, corporate information security policies, procedures, and controls are not enough to prevent data/information loss through a lack of employee awareness about the risks related to handling information. Therefore, effective training and awareness mechanisms are crucial in these organizations as the risks to which they are exposed, for instance, threats linked to information security and security attacks such as phishing, spam, spyware, password spraying, keylogger, social engineering, shoulder surfing, Man-in-the-Middle Attack, Identity theft, Malware , and cybercrime may all result in considerable inconvenience and possible financial loss to the victims as well as damage to the organization itself.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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